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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Navigating Digital Transformation in Emerging Economies: Evidence from Nigerian Entrepreneurial Activities

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ABSTRACT

Digital technologies present opportunities for growth and competitiveness, although its adoption is constrained by infrastructural gaps and systemic challenges. This study investigates the impact of digital transformation on entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria characterized with a low-infrastructure economy. A descriptive survey design was employed, drawing data from 200 entrepreneurs across urban and rural areas using structured questionnaires. Descriptive and inferential statistics, such as Pearson correlation, regression, and t-tests, were applied for analysis. Correlation results show a significant positive relationship between digital transformation and entrepreneurial growth ($r = .413^*$; $p < .05$). Infrastructural deficits such as poor internet, electricity and limited access to digital devices ($\beta = -.217$; $t = 2.552$; $p < 0.05$), ($\beta = -.204$; $t = 2.151$; $p < 0.05$) and ($\beta = -.130$; $t = 1.419$; $p < 0.05$ respectively) hinder the full technology adoption. Digital literacy emerged as a key determinant of effective technology use effectively ($P\text{-value} .007 < 0.05$). The study concludes by highlighting the need for stronger policy implementation, improved infrastructure, inclusive training, and gender-sensitive programs to advance digital entrepreneurship. Recommendations are provided to promote a more inclusive and digitally empowered entrepreneurial landscape in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS

Digital Transformation, Entrepreneurship in Nigeria, Low-infrastructure Economy, Digital Literacy

INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation has emerged as a powerful force reshaping global economies, business models, and entrepreneurial activities in this 21st century. It encompasses the adoption and integration of digital technologies into all areas of human and economic development, fundamentally changing how value is delivered to customers and how businesses operate (Chiemeke & Imafiar, 2020). For developing nations like Nigeria, the rise of digital transformation holds significant promise for

unlocking entrepreneurial potential, driving innovation, and improving competitiveness (Eneanya, 2023). However, the benefits of this digital revolution are often tempered by persistent infrastructural challenges that limit its full exploitation (Omodafe & Onobrakpeya, 2024; Egunjobi, 2025). In a country grappling with unreliable power supply, limited internet penetration in rural areas, and a digital skills gap, the interplay between technological advancement and

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infrastructural deficit presents a paradox for Nigerian entrepreneurs (Akinwale & Olaopa, 2020).

The entrepreneurial spirit among Nigerians is widely acknowledged, with a significant portion of the population engaging in small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs). According to the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN, 2021), there are over 39 million SMEs in Nigeria, accounting for 96% of all businesses in the country and contributing to about 48% of the national GDP. These enterprises are increasingly recognizing the importance of digital tools and platforms in enhancing productivity, expanding markets, and improving service delivery. From online retailing and digital banking to agro-tech and health-tech solutions, Nigerian entrepreneurs are creatively leveraging digital platforms to respond to local challenges and global opportunities (Eze et al., 2021).

Despite these developments, Nigeria's digital landscape is still evolving. Moreover, the high cost of internet data, unreliable electricity supply, and inconsistent government policy frameworks further constrain digital transformation efforts (Jimoh, et. al., 2022). Additionally, frequent power outages compel many business owners to rely on costly alternative energy sources, which erode their profits and operational efficiency. Nonetheless, digital transformation has opened up numerous opportunities that are reshaping the entrepreneurial terrain in Nigeria. The rise of fintech, for example, has democratized financial services and enhanced financial inclusion, especially for previously unbanked populations. Mobile money platforms such as OPay, Paga, and Flutterwave have revolutionized payment systems, enabling micro-businesses to process transactions seamlessly. These digital tools are helping businesses to bypass traditional brick-and-mortar limitations and access broader customer bases (Adeleke and Owolabi, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

Olatunji (2020) argued that in recent years, digital transformation has redefined the global business landscape, creating new opportunities for entrepreneurs to innovate, scale, and compete in both local and international markets. In Nigeria, the emergence of digital tools such as mobile money, social media marketing, e-commerce platforms, and digital service delivery has shown potential to revolutionize entrepreneurial activities, especially among youths and small business owners. However, this potential is yet to be fully realized due to the persistent infrastructural and systemic challenges that characterize the Nigerian economy (Jimoh, et. al., 2022). Among the major issues are the inadequacies of digital infrastructure across the country characterized by poor internet connectivity, high data costs, unreliable electricity supply, and limited access to digital devices, which hinders many entrepreneurs from adopting and sustaining digital tools in their businesses.

Another significant challenge lies in the low level of digital literacy among entrepreneurs (Nakpodia, et. al., 2023). Many business owners lack the skills to effectively utilize available digital technologies, thereby widening the gap between potential and actual impact. To fully harness the transformative potential of digital technology, there is a need for a holistic approach that addresses both technological and infrastructural challenges. Further, existing research has focused more on digital technology adoption in urban startups and corporate organizations,

leaving a knowledge gap on how entrepreneurs in low-infrastructure settings navigate these challenges. This study, therefore, seeks to bridge this gap by exploring the influence of digital transformation on Nigerian entrepreneurial activities within a low infrastructure economy, identifying both the opportunities and the barriers.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the influence of digital transformation on Nigerian entrepreneurial activities, particularly within the context of a low infrastructure economy. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the relationship between digital transformation and the growth of entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria.
2. Analyze the major digital infrastructural constraints that hinder the effective adoption of digital tools by Nigerian entrepreneurs.
3. Assess the effect of digital literacy on entrepreneurs' ability to utilize digital technologies effectively.

Research Hypotheses

- H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between digital transformation and the growth of entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria.
- H₀₂: Digital infrastructure challenges do not significantly affect the adoption of digital tools by Nigerian entrepreneurs.
- H₀₃: Digital literacy has no significant influence on entrepreneurs' ability to utilize digital technologies effectively.

Significance of the study

The study offers valuable insights into how digital transformation influences entrepreneurial activities within a developing, low infrastructure economy like Nigeria, and how entrepreneurs navigate both the opportunities and the constraints it presents. For entrepreneurs and small business owners, the study provides a clearer understanding of how digital tools and platforms such as mobile apps, e-commerce, social media, and digital payment systems can be effectively leveraged for business growth. By highlighting practical strategies for overcoming infrastructural limitations, the study aim to empower entrepreneurs, especially those in rural and underserved areas, to participate more actively in the digital economy.

Furthermore, academics and researchers in the fields of entrepreneurship, digital transformation, and development studies can use this study as a foundation for further research. It contributes to existing literature by focusing on the unique Nigerian experience and the challenges faced by entrepreneurs in low-infrastructure environments. Ultimately, this study supports Nigeria's broader goal of building a digitally inclusive economy by identifying pathways to support innovation, reduce the digital divide, and promote sustainable entrepreneurship.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital Transformation

Digital transformation refers to the process by which organizations and individuals integrate digital technology into all areas of business and daily life, fundamentally altering how they operate and deliver value (Ajiri, Osahon & Demaki, 2025). In the context of entrepreneurship, digital transformation includes adopting tools such as mobile applications, e-commerce platforms, social media marketing, cloud computing, digital payments, and data analytics to enhance efficiency and customer experience (Egunjobi, 2025). In Nigeria, digital transformation has gained momentum with the increase in mobile phone usage, fintech innovations, and online service platforms like Jumia, Paystack, and Flutterwave (Omodafe & Onobrakpeya, 2024). However, the level of adoption varies widely due to infrastructural challenges, especially in rural areas (Akinwale & Olaopa, 2020).

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship involves the identification and exploitation of business opportunities through the creation and management of new ventures. Entrepreneurs play a crucial role in job creation, poverty reduction, and innovation (Schumpeter, 1934). In Nigeria, entrepreneurship is largely driven by necessity rather than opportunity, with many individuals turning to small businesses as a means of survival due to high unemployment rates (Adebayo & Olayemi, 2021). The digital age presents new possibilities for Nigerian entrepreneurs to grow their businesses through wider market access, automation, and digital customer engagement.

Challenges of Digital Entrepreneurship Adoption in Nigeria

Digital entrepreneurship in Nigeria holds significant potential to drive economic growth, innovation, and job creation (Amadi & Obele, 2023). However, several constraints such as high cost of internet access, unreliable electricity supply, low digital literacy and limited last-mile connectivity, among many others continue to hinder the full realization of digital entrepreneurship, thereby, limiting technology-intensive ventures such as e-commerce, logistics and cloud services (Nkwo & Eniege, 2024; NCC Consultancy review, 2024; Omodafe & Onobrakpeya, 2024; Egunjobi, 2025) Many aspiring entrepreneurs lack the necessary skills to navigate digital ecosystems, limiting their competitiveness. Access to financing is also limited, with many digital startups unable to secure funding due to stringent loan requirements or lack of investor interest in tech ventures. Lastly, weak policy implementation and inconsistent regulatory frameworks pose barriers to growth. (Ajayi, 2021).

Theoretical Review

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), created by Fred Davis in 1989, is a popular theoretical framework that describes how people learn to embrace and use technology. Perceived usage (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) are the two primary characteristics that TAM identifies as influencing a user's decision to adopt a technology. The degree to which an individual thinks that utilizing a specific technology would improve their productivity or job performance is known as

perceived usefulness. Contrarily, perceived ease of use describes how much a person thinks utilizing the technology would be effortless. These two ideas have an impact on how someone feels about utilizing the technology, which in turn influences how they intend to use it and, ultimately, how they actually use it. This approach is very useful for comprehending how Nigerian business owners behave online. When customers recognize the obvious advantages and find the technologies easy to use, many are willing to embrace digital platforms like digital payment systems, e-commerce websites, or mobile apps. On the other hand, adoption rates fall when people believe that digital platforms are complicated or useless. Thus, TAM provides insightful information on the different degrees of digital tool adoption among business owners in Nigeria's changing business environment.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory

Proposed by Rogers (1962), the Diffusion of Innovation Theory explains how new ideas and technologies spread through cultures and societies. The theory categorizes adopters into innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards. In the Nigerian context, urban entrepreneurs with access to infrastructure and exposure tend to be early adopters of digital tools, while rural entrepreneurs often fall into the late majority or laggard category due to infrastructural and educational barriers.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive survey design to explore how digital transformation affects entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria, particularly among entrepreneurs in the retail and telecommunications sectors in Oyo State. The focus was on small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) owners, startups, fintech operators, and informal digital vendors who are currently using or planning to use digital technologies in their businesses. A total of 200 respondents were chosen through stratified and purposive sampling methods to ensure that both retail and telecommunications entrepreneurs with relevant digital experience were represented. Data collection was carried out using a structured questionnaire, which was rated on a five-point Likert scale from Strongly Agree (1) to Strongly Disagree (5). Experts validated the instrument, and it was pre-tested with 20 entrepreneurs to confirm its reliability and clarity. For data analysis, both descriptive statistics (like frequency and percentage) and inferential statistics (including Pearson correlation and regression analysis) were employed, with hypotheses tested at a significance level of 0.05 to assess the relationship between digital transformation and entrepreneurial performance.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Analysis of Respondents Bio Data

Table 1: Demographic Information of Respondents

Demographic Features	Features	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18-25years	50	25.0%
	26-35years	76	38.0%
	36-45years	42	21.0%
	46years and above	32	16.0%
Gender	Male	118	59.0%
	Female	82	41.0%
Nature of Business	Supermarkets	49	24.5%
	Retail Stores	31	15.5%
	Telecommunication	52	26.0%
	Logistics	29	14.5%
	Others	52	19.5%
Marital Status	Single	88	44.0%
	Married	100	50.0%
	Divorced	12	6.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 showed the demographic information of the respondents. The largest segment (38%) is aged **26–35 years**, reflecting a generation of **young, energetic, and digitally inclined entrepreneurs**. The data shows a male-dominated entrepreneurial landscape (59%), though female representation (41%) is also significant. This indicates a growing inclusion of women in the digital economy. The nature of the business reflect a dominance of business in the telecommunication industry, this is reflects the importance of technology in entrepreneurship development in an economy like Nigeria. While the marital status shows a larger percentage (55%) of entrepreneurs are married. This implies that being married does not affect entrepreneurial activities among the Nigerian entrepreneurs.

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between digital transformation and the growth of entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria.

Table 2: Pearson’s Correlation between Digital Transformation and Growth of Entrepreneurial Activities

Variables	N	Mean	S.D	Df	R	Sig.	Decision
Digital Transformation	200	19.77	3.86	198	.413*	.000	Rejected
Entrepreneurial Growth	200	13.42	1.61				

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Results on Table 2 revealed a moderate positive correlation between digital transformation and growth of entrepreneurial activities ($r =$

.413*; $p < .05$). This suggests that digital transformation in a pointer to entrepreneurial growth in Nigeria. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Digital infrastructure challenges do not significantly affect the adoption of digital tools by Nigerian entrepreneurs.

Table 3: Multiple Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	2.579	.221		
Poor Internet	-.217	.085	.254	2.552	.012
Electricity	-.204	.081	.233	2.151	.010
Limited Access to Digital Devices	-.130	.071	.142	1.419	.009

$R = .280^a$; $R \text{ Square} = 0.79$, $Adjusted \text{ R Square} = 0.65$

Independent Variable: Poor Internet, Electricity, Limited Access to Digital Devices

Dependent Variable: Adoption of digital tools by Nigerian entrepreneurs

The table presents the digital infrastructure challenges affecting the adoption of digital tools by Nigerian Entrepreneurs. The table shows that the independent variables (poor internet, electricity and limited access to digital devices) made a significant hindrance to the adoption of digital tools by Nigerian Entrepreneurs. In term of magnitude, Poor internet made the most significant hindrance ($\beta = -.217$; $t = 2.552$; $p < 0.05$) to the adoption of digital tools by Nigerian entrepreneurs, followed by Poor electricity ($\beta = -.204$; $t = 2.151$; $p < 0.05$) then followed by limited access to digital devices ($\beta = -.130$; $t = 1.419$; $p < 0.05$). This implies that, an increase in the independent variables e.g.

Poor internet, Poor electricity, and Limited Access to Digital Devices will lead to a decrease on Adoption of digital tools.

H₀₃: Digital literacy has no significant influence on entrepreneurs' ability to utilize digital technologies effectively.

Table 4: Regression Analysis on Digital Literacy and Entrepreneurs' Ability to Utilize Digital Technologies Effectively.

Model	Regression
Sum of Squares	1126.840
Df	1
Mean Square	1126.840
F	7.532
Sig.	.007 ^b
T- values	2.013
P> T-values	.0000**

Table 4 shows the regression analysis on digital literacy and entrepreneurs' ability to utilize digital technologies effectively. The table shows that digital literacy significantly influences entrepreneurs' ability to utilize digital technologies effectively (P-value .007 < 0.05). Also, the P> T-values (.0000) suggest there is a positive and significant relationship between digital literacy and entrepreneurs' ability to utilize digital technologies effectively. The T-Value of 2.013 also confirmed the significance of the model.

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study reveal that digital transformation has a statistically significant positive effect on entrepreneurial growth in Nigeria. A moderate positive correlation ($r = .413$, $p < .05$) indicates that the adoption of digital tools such as e-commerce, mobile apps, and digital payments fosters business expansion and market reach. This corroborate the findings of Ogbevoen, (2025) who found that the adoption of e-commerce and digital platforms tools enables SMEs in Nigeria to overcome structural constraints, lower transaction costs and expand market reach beyond regional confines. However, infrastructural challenges such as poor internet connectivity, irregular electricity supply, and limited access to digital devices significantly hinder digital adoption. This is supported by the findings of Okunola, (2024) who found that poor unreliable internet, technical capability issues, and poor digital infrastructure are the major barriers to technology adoption by Nigerian SMEs. Additionally, digital literacy was shown to significantly and positively affect entrepreneurs' ability to use digital technologies effectively. This result align with the findings of Umetiti et al., (2025) who found that entrepreneurs' levels of digital literacy critically shape their ability to leverage digital tools and affect business performance. These findings underscore the dual reality of opportunity and constraint in Nigeria's digital entrepreneurial landscape, especially within low-infrastructure contexts.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that digital transformation significantly influences entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria, offering both opportunities and challenges, especially within the context of a low-infrastructure economy. The findings revealed that digital tools play a vital role in enhancing business growth, market expansion, and customer engagement. However, these benefits have not well benefited by entrepreneurs across sectors due to infrastructural limitations like poor internet connectivity, unstable electricity supply, and limited access to digital devices. Furthermore, digital literacy emerged as a key determinant of successful digital adoption, emphasizing the need for continuous training and capacity-building programs.

Overall, digital transformation has the potential to revolutionize Nigeria's entrepreneurial landscape, but its success depends on inclusive infrastructure development, accessible digital education, and sustained policy commitment. Improvement in this regard will not only enhance economic inclusion but also position Nigeria to fully harness the potentials of a digital economy in fostering innovation, job creation, and sustainable development.

Recommendations

1. The government should invest in affordable, high-speed internet and stable electricity, especially in rural and semi-urban areas
2. Collaborations with telecom and other companies can accelerate infrastructure rollout and financial inclusion.
3. Tailored digital empowerment programs should target female entrepreneurs to close the gender gap in digital adoption.

References

- Adeleke, I. T., & Owolabi, A. (2020). Barriers to digital entrepreneurship in developing economies: A Nigerian perspective. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management*, 24(4-5), 301–318.
- Ajayi, A. I. (2021). Digital transformation and the Nigerian economy: Challenges and prospects for entrepreneurs. *Journal of African Business*, 22(3), 412–429.
- Ajiri, J. I., Osahon, H. O., & Demaki, G. O. (2025). Digital transformation technology as determinants of business performance of SMEs in Edo and Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 13(04)
- Akinwale, Y. O., & Olaopa, R. O. (2020). The role of digital infrastructure in promoting innovation among SMEs in Nigeria. *African Journal of Economic Policy*, 27(1), 55–70.
- Amadi, L., & Obele, L. (2023). Digital entrepreneurship and sustainable business growth of SMEs in Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 13(04).
- Chiemeke, S. C., & Imafidor, M. O. (2020). An assessment of the impact of digital technology adoption on economic growth and labour

- productivity in Nigeria. *Economic Research and Electronic Network*, 21(1) 103 – 128.
- Eze, S. C., Chinedu-Eze, V. C., & Bello, A. O. (2021). Digital entrepreneurship and innovation in Africa: Challenges and opportunities. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 164, 120490.
- Egunjobi, A.T. (2025). Digital entrepreneurship: Strategy for curbing youth unemployment in Lagos, Nigeria. *Lagos Journal of Banking, Finance and Economic Issues*, 4(1)
- Jimoh, C. A., Akintunde, A. O., Ogundiya, A., & Mustapha S. A (2022). Evaluation of Factors Influencing Entrepreneurial Development in Nigerian Medium-Scale Foods and Beverages. *African Multidisciplinary Journal of Development (AMJD)*, 11(3), 230-242
- Nakpodia, F., Ashiru, F., Jing You, J., & Oni, O. (2023). Digital technologies, social entrepreneurship and resilience during crisis in developing countries: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 29(2), 342-368.
- Ndukwe, I. G. (2022). Internet accessibility and digital business performance in Nigeria: A study of SMEs. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 29(1), 88–105.
- Nkwo, F. N., & Eneiga, R. U. (2024). Entrepreneurship development in Nigeria: Overcoming challenges and expanding opportunities in the digital economy. *SADI International Journal of Management and Accounting*, 11(3), 18 – 32
- NNC. (2024). *Consultancy Study on Developing Sustainable Digital Entrepreneurship Business Model in a Digital Nigeria*. (final report). Nigerian Communication Commission.
- Ogbevoen, F. E. (2025). The role of digital platforms and e-commerce in accelerating SME internalization: Evidence from Nigerian SMEs. *Econova: A Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 1-13.
- Olatunji, O. C. (2020). Digital inclusion and financial technology adoption in Nigeria. *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*, 12(3), 295–303.
- Omodafe, P. U. & Onobrakpeya, S. A. (2024). Digital transformation and business model innovation: Insights from multinational companies in South-South Nigeria. *African Journal of Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 14(8)
- Okunola, C. O. (2024). Barriers to technology adoption among small and medium enterprises. *International Journal of Finance, Economics, and Management Studies*, 2(1), 103-114.
- Umetiti, C. B., Nwafor, A. E., Arachie, A. E., & Ifeme, A. P. (2025). Digital literacy in the context of small and medium enterprises (SMEs): A performance dynamics. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research*, 11(1). 1-17.
- Westerman, G., Bonnet, D., & McAfee, A. (2014). *Leading digital: Turning technology into business transformation*. Harvard Business Review Press

